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MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES

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**KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES OF THE SAMAHAN NG
MANGINGISDA NG PURO-SINALIKAWAY (SAMAPUSI INC.) IN A
COLLABORATIVE MANAGEMENT OF BUNTOD REEF MARINE SANCTUARY,
CITY OF MASBATE**

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29TH May 2023

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
- III The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

ENGR. RODOLFO R. AJERO JR.

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the level of understanding, behavior, and collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary among members of the fisher organization, Samahan ng Mangingisda ng Puro Sinalikway. Through a comprehensive Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) survey, data was collected on participants' knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to marine resource conservation and sustainable management. The results revealed that the fisher organization members had a moderate level of knowledge regarding collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems. They displayed awareness of the importance of marine resources and exhibited familiarity with specific ecosystems such as mangroves, seagrasses, and coral reefs. However, there were knowledge gaps, particularly in understanding biodiversity and the ecological functions of various ecosystems.

In terms of attitudes, participants generally held positive views towards marine resource management and expressed a willingness to engage in conservation efforts. They acknowledged the significant benefits that marine resources provided to their lives, livelihoods, and the local economy. Nonetheless, certain negative attitudes towards regulations and policies related to marine conservation were identified, which could impede effective management practices. Regarding practices, fisher organization members demonstrated commendable behavior in sustainable fishing and marine resource management. They utilized environmentally friendly fishing gear and employed responsible fishing methods. However, improvements were needed in waste disposal practices and the prevention of damage to coral reefs and other marine ecosystems.

The findings emphasized the importance of education and awareness initiatives to address knowledge gaps and enhance the understanding of fisher organization members regarding their role in marine habitat protection. Furthermore, promoting collaborative shared management among fisher organizations and stakeholders was crucial for effective protection and management of marine habitats. To enhance the management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary, policy recommendations included increasing education and awareness efforts, encouraging community participation in conservation initiatives, regular monitoring and evaluation of environmental programs, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and providing more funding and support for conservation efforts. Implementing these recommendations would strengthen the conservation and protection of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary's marine resources, benefiting the fisherfolk community and the environment as a whole.

Keywords: Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary, Marine Resource Conservation, Sustainable Management, Fisher Organization, Marine Ecosystems, Collaborative Shared Management, Environmental Awareness, Community Engagement, Marine Habitat Protection, Stakeholder Collaboration, Knowledge, Attitude and Practices (KAP) Survey.

I. INTRODUCTION

The City of Masbate, a locality that is enriched by the sea, has a population of 104,522 (2020, PSA Census on Population) with total of 13% of household dependent on fishing as their main livelihood (2022, FishR Masbate City). The implementation of coastal resources management program of the City Government of Masbate will measure their initiatives especially in ensuring food security and livelihood opportunity, how these stakeholders respond to their responsibility in a collaborative shared governance practices specifically the fisherfolk organization into coastal resources management when in terms of their knowledge, attitude and practices. In year 2001 the City Government of Masbate formulated the Integrated Coastal Management Plan to protect and recognize the importance of coastal ecosystem as a source of food, materials and income, especially for the low-income groups which is the fishers. The potential of coastal resources in the development of coastal eco-tourism, and other economic activities will definitely improve the city's socio-economic well-being.

The local government unit has the authority to manage the municipal water within its jurisdiction. Republic Act 10654 provides a framework for the development, management, and conservation of the country's fisheries. It reaffirms the jurisdiction of the city governments over municipal waters and emphasizes their important roles in enforcing fishery laws and managing coastal resources. These provisions support the establishment of marine protected areas, giving local government units the authority to declare and manage areas as such. The Code mandates local government units to set aside at least 15% of their municipal waters for fish sanctuaries and decentralizes certain functions of the national government by granting extensive power to local governments to manage their coastal and marine resources up to 15 kilometers offshore. Municipal marine sanctuaries or marine protected areas can be

established solely through a municipal or city ordinance without the need for national government approval.

The Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary was established by City Ordinance No. 021-01, which established a marine sanctuary within the municipal waters of Masbate City on July 10, 2002. Its purpose is to protect biodiversity within the municipal waters of the City of Masbate and to allow for the buildup of fish abundance and biomass in order to export fish to areas outside of the marine sanctuary. The name "Buntod" comes from a Visayan word meaning "small hill". It is called Buntod because of the white sand bar that bulges at the western portion of the shoal in the middle of the sea. Fishermen from Masbate City and other municipalities use Buntod Reef as a common fishing ground due to its richness and abundance in terms of fishery resources. However, due to the increasing population, the consumption of fishery resources for food and livelihood has also increased. This dilemma has led to a drastic increase in fishing pressure at Buntod Reef, to the point where almost all fishermen are using illegal and destructive methods to catch the fishery resources in the area (Buntod Management Plan, 2019).

The Samahan ng Mangigisda ng Puro Sinalikway (SAMAPUS) Inc, is a Security Exchange Commission (SEC) registered association with registration number CN 2000829882 dated 15th of August 2008. This organization is a sole co-manager fisherfolk organization of the City Government of Masbate City in managing the Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. Fishing is a primary source of livelihood and dependency by all its members to sea. As a strategy to restore the partially degraded marine and coastal resources the local government took the lead to transform these offenders into partners. This initiative paved way to the formation of Bantay Dagat Task Force with SAMAPUSI members as one of the partners in securing the Coastal

and Marine Resources specifically for Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. This harmonious working relationship between the City Government of Masbate City and SAMAPUSI Inc. has resulted to positive outcomes. Because of the proper management of marine protected areas, the organization established ecotourism enterprise entitled “The Reef Discovery” as one of the alternative livelihood income of the organization. This enterprise contribute in the poverty reduction by creating direct or indirect economic opportunities to fisherfolk and community.

It is commendable that the Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary was recognized as the best outstanding locally managed marine protected area during the Para El Mar (For the Sea) awards and recognition in 2019. The effective management by the City Government of Masbate and the partnership with the community in a shared governance of the marine protected areas were highlighted during the competition. Given this recognition, it is important to understand how the fisherfolk organization, SAMAPUSI Inc., became a champion in managing the resources and how the City Government of Masbate City was able to transform them from offenders to protectors of the sea. This study aims to dive deeper into the stakeholders' perspectives, specifically the fisherfolk organization, and to examine the strategies employed by the local government to engage and empower the community to become responsible protectors of the marine and coastal resources.

The result of Management Effective Assessment Tool for the Marine Protected Area. The Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary result a rating of level four (4), accompanied by a flawless total score of 84 points, exemplifies the dedication and meticulous management efforts put forth by the City Government of Masbate and SAMAPUSI, the local organization responsible for managing the reef. Each management focus area has received a remarkable 100% rating, underscoring the

comprehensive approach taken to safeguard the MPA's ecological integrity and sustainable use.

Their collaborative efforts have not only protected the marine resources but also ensured the prosperity of the local community. By generating internal revenues sufficient to cover operational expenses, support the livelihoods of the PO members managing the MPA, and advocate for the protection of other MPAs within the municipal waters, Buntod Reef has become a self-sustaining entity. Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary stands as an exemplar of effective marine conservation and community empowerment. Through its perfect score and unwavering commitment to management focus areas, Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary has demonstrated the positive outcomes that can be achieved when local communities and governmental bodies work hand in hand. The success of Buntod Reef has not only enriched the marine ecosystems but has also uplifted the lives of those involved, spurring further initiatives and inspiring replication of conservation efforts in Masbate City. As we celebrate the accomplishments of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary, let us recognize its significance as a beacon of hope and a shining example of what can be accomplished when conservation and community unite for a sustainable future.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Human relationship to environment is an important factor towards its management. The human is the center of everything that makes our resources attain sustainability. Our decision as human, and how we interact to our environment will define our future. One of the strategies in managing the coastal resources is the community based coastal resources management approach which is the process in involving local resources users and community members in active management and taking full responsibility for the process of the coastal resources' management planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation.

Involvement of fishermen in the management of coastal resources. The effect evaluation of community-based coastal resource management initiatives in the Philippines was studied by Pomeroy et al. in 1996. The advantages of delegating control over coastal resource management to local governments and resource users have long been understood, but the ideal systems for managing coastal resource management rely on a variety of circumstances. Early in the 1980s, a number of programs including community-based management and co-management were launched in the Philippines. In order to establish where improvements might be made in the design of upcoming community-based coastal resource management projects, this research compares and contrasts these programs.

One of the elements that contributes to the conception, implementation, and evaluation of the project's success is the early and ongoing involvement of the project's beneficiaries. Collaboration and knowledge networks in the management of coastal resources. How important stakeholders cooperate in the implementation of marine protected areas with varied uses. This study focused on the examination of

organizational networks and stakeholders for the management and suggested multiple uses of the marine protected area. The study demonstrated that social networks and their characteristics are crucial in the quest for explanations for the effectiveness of natural resource governance and management. Using a coastal marine ecosystem in northern Chile as an example, the study of the structure and characteristics of interorganizational social networks engaged in the use and management of natural resources.

The two network topologies that were investigated were the first ones involving relationships of collaboration and the second ones involving the transmission and exchange of scientific knowledge and information important to the management of natural resources and the associated decision-making process. poor values of centralization and density in both networks indicated a poor flow of collaborative and exchange linkages among many stakeholders, and both networks displayed little cohesion.

The actors and actresses in a scene make unique decisions on how to best fit into the scene, and those decisions will either lead to success or failure. Successful decisions gradually become the norm for the group as a whole, and they may even become collective behaviors. Unsuccessful tactics are not used by others and may even wind up being forbidden in the group. Therefore, culture would be the collection of unique adaptive tactics used by members of a group. When a strategy is effective, others in the group adopt it, whereas when a strategy fails, the group discourages others from adopting it or else relegates it to social taboo.

Similar to social theory, environment management has two main purposes. The first is to explain why people care so much about the environment and how it may be managed to their advantage. They might alter specific environmental elements to

serve their needs and respond to environmental changes. The activities and behaviors within the habitats, as well as how we perceive and communicate with one another as individuals or groups, are only one more element of the ecosystem that makes up human ecology. How human perspectives impact our ecosystem. The ecosystem-based model of human ecology makes the assumption that human populations, as a socially cohesive whole, mold their behavior in order to survive as long as possible in an ecosystem.

In response to the management of coastal resources, fishermen's responsibilities. In order to achieve sustainable exploitation of natural resources, the Chilean government has implemented a program that grants organized groups of artisanal fisher's formal property rights over specified regions of the seabed. The body of research on the significance of attitudes toward co-management and conservation of marine resources among artisanal fishers. To understand the significance in the planning and execution of fisheries management, the measured disparities in the attitudes of participating artisanal fishermen regarding the form of management. Surveys and participatory rural evaluation methods were employed in the study to interview members of six fishery management committees.

In three key areas opinions toward the environment, unsolved issues with the management area policy, and perceived benefits fishers' attitudes varied dramatically among syndicates. These discrepancies showed that different world views exist that shape how fishers behave in relation to the marine environment and its management. Additionally, the degree of off-sector pluriactivity and the fishermen's reliance on diving as a source of revenue were best connected with the responses they provided. This showed that the best way to adopt dual conservation/management approaches in Chilean artisanal fisheries would be to take a livelihood strategy that takes into account

the various economic niches of the fishers. There is strong evidence that participatory governance is essential for dealing with complicated issues of managing for many values and outcomes in order to achieve ecological sustainability and economic growth.

The Oceans Act of Canada and federal oceans policy offer a solid framework for community-based management of coastal and vast ocean resources and participatory governance. Although the Oceans Act and Oceans Policy have contributed to certain steps toward participatory governance, the means for a significant role for communities in integrated coastal and ocean management (ICOM) have not been effectively established. Nine initiatives are suggested in order to improve and expand community involvement in ICOM: (1) paradigm shifts; (2) overcoming "turf protection"; (3) ensuring compatibility of goals; (4) ensuring sufficient information; (5) addressing internal community stratification; (6) creating cross-scale linkages; (7) creating a participatory policy environment; (8) building community capacity; and (9) monitoring and evaluating local-level initiatives.

As each environment has its own opportunities and constraints, human existence will vary. According to the model, human populations that live in diverse ecosystems over time will develop a variety of cultural features that, either alone or in certain combinations, would represent the best means of ensuring the populations' survival in that ecosystem. The link between social systems and ecosystems is highlighted by the theory of human ecology as being distinct yet interdependent. This will emphasize collective behavior, culture, and be viewed as the accumulation of individual decisions on how to behave in an environment in order to conform to the actor and actress-based model of human ecology.

One of the key elements in managing our environment is the leaders. Political commitment to making wise choices that will preserve our resources and lead to a happy relationship with our environment. They have the authority to decide how resources are distributed among all other persons and groups in the population, allowing for shared control of the resources. Political ecology is crucial to this study because it will determine how the stakeholders react to a shared responsibility for managing the coastal resources. According to this idea, a population's members hold the power. The populace itself both creates and legitimizes it. Power brokers are thought to be interested in ensuring that the population as a whole finally gets to adapt to its environment to the best of their abilities, to increase the well-being of their constituents, particularly as this strengthens the power broker's ability to retain power.

The 2006 study by Savitree Rangsihaht and Supaporn Thaipakdee, "Problem Analyses for Planning Fisheries Extension Programs: Tools and Methods." The diminishing state of fishing resources was a major issue that participants addressed and examined in the study using methods of problem analysis based on the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) survey. The usefulness and implementation of the KAP survey were viewed well by the participants.

They provided an explanation of how to perform the KAP survey due to its significance, potential for resolving disputes, and advantages for fishermen's livelihood. The goals of this study were to: 1) identify the fundamental traits of participants; 2) present the problem-analysis tools and methods that participants had discussed; 3) show participants' perceptions of the usefulness and actual use of these tools and methods; and 4) describe the rationale behind participants' decision to use these tools and methods. Twenty-six trainees took part in the international training course in coastal fisheries management and extension methodology, which was run

from August 22 to September 21 by the Southeast Asian Fisheries Development Center (SEAFDEC).

The following findings were made: 1) Fisheries officials who were directly involved in the program design made up the majority of participants. They had worked for an average of 7.44 years. 2) The participants' tools and methodologies demonstrated how to analyze problems based on the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) survey. One of the main issues that attendees discussed and examined was the depletion of fisheries resources. Participants 3) stated their good opinions on the usefulness and implementation of the KAP survey, and 4) explained why the survey should be implemented since it is crucial for resolving disputes and improving the livelihood of fisherman. (Rangsipaht and Thaipakdee, 2006)

A survey technique known as knowledge, attitude, and practices measures the phenomenon of human life as well as its influence on behavior and how it affects environmental management. The Case of Indonesia: Environmental Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices for University Student Behavior Change by Erwinsyah, E. Focus on the study in 2022 that will look at the connections between college students' environmental knowledge, attitudes, and practices, as well as how these affect behavior change. A statistical non-parametric bivariate Pearson Correlation is the method used to analyze the data. According to the study's findings, 63 percent of students acquired their environmental knowledge through official educational channels, 15 percent through non-formal education, and 22 percent through mixed formal and informal channels.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this study is to investigate the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices of the Samahan ng Mangingisda ng Puro-Sinalikway towards the collaborative management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary located in the City of Masbate. The study aims to identify the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices of the fisherfolk towards the management of the sanctuary and to explore the factors that affect their participation in collaborative management. The study will use a survey questionnaire to gather data from the respondents and will employ statistical tools to analyze the results.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are to assess the level of understanding and behavior of the stakeholders specifically the fisher organization members of Samahan ng Mangingisda ng Puro Sinalikway, their knowledge, attitude and practices in a collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. Specifically, it aims to:

1. Determine the knowledge, attitude and practices of fisherfolk organization members in terms of collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems.
2. Assessing fisherfolk organization members and evaluate the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of fisherfolk organization members regarding their role in protecting the marine habitat in Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary.
3. Provide policy recommendations based on the findings of the study that can enhance the implementation and effectiveness management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary.

V. RATIONALE

The study is expected to provide valuable insights for the City Government of Masbate City and other marine protected area managers in developing effective strategies for ensuring the sustainability of coastal resources management. By exploring the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and practices of the stakeholders, particularly the members of the fisherfolk organization, towards collaborative management practices, the study can help identify the factors that influence their response to co-management by the local government units.

The findings of the study can also contribute to the development of sustainable management activities in marine protected areas. By understanding the current practices of the fisherfolk organization members in managing Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary, including their level of participation and compliance with regulations, the study can provide insights into how to encourage sustainable fishing practices and promote the effective management of marine resources.

Overall, the study can provide valuable information to stakeholders and decision-makers on how to improve the effectiveness of collaborative management practices with the community, specifically the fisherfolk organization, in managing marine protected areas. This can lead to more sustainable and resilient coastal ecosystems, better livelihoods for fishing communities, and a healthier ocean for future generations.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The study will investigate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the fisherfolk organization members of SAMAPUSI Inc. in the City of Masbate, specifically as co-managers of the Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary in a collaborative shared governance with the City Government. The study will be limited to the perspectives and experiences of the fisherfolk organization members and their knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The study aims to provide insights into effective strategies for collaborative shared governance in managing marine protected areas and inform decision-making and policy development towards sustainable management of coastal resources.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary is located at Barangay Nursery, City of Masbate. With the total area of two hundred fifty hectares (250 ha.) A diverse habitat composed of coral reefs, seagrass beds, mangroves and beach front. With the core zone of 51.42 hectares and the buffer zone of 198.58 hectares. (Buntod Management Plan, 2019)

Figure 1. Map of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary.

The study will focus on the fisherfolk organization or the Samahang Mangingisda ng Purok Sinalikway (SAMAPUSI Inc), is one of the active people's organization, a non-stock and non-profit association registered to Security and Exchange Commission. The purposes of the association incorporated are to have a strong and progressive fisherfolk association, to improve the quality of life and promote unity and self-esteem and respect among members and community as a

whole. The main advocacy is in the protection of environment and management of fishery and coastal resources in the municipal waters of Masbate City.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

Population

Fishing is a primary source of livelihood and dependency by all its members to sea. Based on the record coming from the City Agriculture Office, City of Masbate a total of thirty five (35) fisherfolk members of the Samahan ng Mangingisda ng Puro-Sinalikway. At present, there were only thirty (30) active members.

Instruments

The knowledge, attitude and practices (KAP) survey forms provided by the DENR Biodiversity Management Bureau (BMB) Technical Bulletin on the guidelines for the KAP Survey were used for the study. The survey form served as a qualitative and quantitative method of data collection used to measure the knowledge, attitude, and practices of stakeholders with respect to the coastal and marine environment. Participants underwent an interview and a consultative consultation and answered a KAP survey questionnaire based on the following:

1. Respondent profile (General Information, Age, Gender, Religion, Civil Status, Number of House Members, Highest Educational Attainment, and Position in the Organization)
2. Their knowledge on biodiversity, the importance of coastal and marine and other ecosystems, different ecosystems in the area, and the importance of marine habitat.
3. Their perception in the protection of the marine habitat and ecosystems, willingness to help with their obligations and responsibilities, and their

participation in the City Government of Masbate in protecting the Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary.

4. Their practices in solid waste management, and their contribution to conservation efforts and advocacy.

Data Gathering and Procedures

The study involved conducting on-site surveys of respondents located in the marine protected area. To ensure convenience and full understanding of the respondents, a completed questionnaire translated to Filipino was used. A digital voice recorder was also used to keep all responses of the respondents for quality and reliable data source, with photo documentation. Time management was a priority, and the researcher was sensitive to time considerations when conducting on-site oral interview surveys. The KAP survey questionnaires were scheduled for a maximum of one to three hours per session. A total of 5-10 days were allotted to complete and to secure the data. Prior to the main survey, a pretesting of the survey questionnaire was done with a minimum of 3-5 fisherfolk to guide any revisions and trial of the questionnaires.

Figure 2. Photos in conducting the onsite survey and interview.

Data analyses

After the data had been collected through the on-site survey of the respondents, the KAP survey questionnaires were carefully examined and processed. The data was organized and analyzed using the software tool of microsoft excel spreadsheet to present the results in an understandable and visually appealing manner. Graphs, charts, averages, and percentages were used to highlight the findings of the study, making it easier to identify trends and patterns of the data. The descriptive statistical tools were used in analyzing the KAP result of the respondents.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thirty (30) respondents altogether, whose ages ranged across different age brackets, provided data for the study. There were no responders between the ages of 15 and 19. Two (2) of the responders were in the 20–24 age range. There were also no respondents in the age range of 25 to 29. Eight (8) respondents, who made up the largest percentage of respondents, were in the 50–54 age group. Nineteen (19) respondents made up the other age groups, with three (3) each from the 35-39 and 55-59 age groups, four (4) from the 45-49 age group, and six (6) from the 30-34 age group. In the meantime, there were three (3) responses from each of the age groups of 40–44 and 60–plus.

Figure 3. Age Bracket.

For gender, all 30 respondents were male, the majority of the respondents (29 out of 30) were Catholic, while one respondent was Baptist. For civil status, 25 respondents were married, four were single, and one was separated. For education, the majority of the respondents (20 out of 30) had completed elementary school, while

seven had completed high school, one had completed college, and one had completed a vocational course.

Figure 4. Education Level.

For the first objective in determining the knowledge, attitude and practices of fisherfolk organization members in terms of collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems. The study found that fisherfolk organization members have a moderate level of knowledge about the concept of collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems. The respondents recognized the importance of marine resources and specific ecosystems such as mangroves, seagrasses, and coral reefs. However, there were gaps in their knowledge, particularly in understanding the different aspects of biodiversity and the ecological functions of different ecosystems.

In terms of attitudes, the study showed that respondents have a positive attitude towards the management of marine resources and are willing to participate in conservation efforts. They recognize the benefits of marine resources to their daily lives, livelihoods, and the economy. However, there are still some negative attitudes

towards regulations and policies related to marine conservation, which may hinder effective management.

In terms of practices, the study found that respondents have good practices towards sustainable fishing and marine resource management. They use fishing gear that is environmentally friendly and practice responsible fishing methods. However, there are still some practices that need improvement, such as proper waste disposal and avoiding damaging coral reefs and other marine ecosystems.

The study of The Perceived Benefits of Marine Protected Areas by Fishers in Batangas, Philippines results found that the fisherfolk in Batangas perceive marine protected areas (MPAs) to have several benefits, including increased fish biomass, improved catch, and increased tourism. The study also revealed that social factors, such as collaboration among fisherfolk, are important determinants of the success of MPAs. However, the study also identified challenges in the management of MPAs, including tourism-related issues, fishing and poaching, pollution, and coastal development. The need for effective management and stakeholder collaboration in the implementation and sustainability of the marine protected areas.

While both studies focus on marine resource management and conservation efforts in the Philippines, they differ in their specific objectives from the perspective of fisherfolk in Batangas, while the study on the knowledge, attitude and practice of the fisherfolk association on the management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary focus towards collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems.

Both studies highlight the importance of stakeholder collaboration and effective management in achieving successful marine conservation efforts. The first study emphasizes the role of social factors, such as collaboration among fisherfolk, in

determining the success of MPAs. The second study highlights the positive attitudes of fisherfolk organization members towards marine resource management and conservation, but also identifies areas where improvements are needed in their knowledge and practices. Overall, both studies provide valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities for marine conservation in the Philippines, and underscore the need for continued efforts towards effective management and stakeholder collaboration.

In assessing fisherfolk organization members and evaluate the level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of fisherfolk organization members regarding their role in protecting the marine habitat in Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. The level of knowledge of fisherfolk organization members regarding their role in protecting the marine habitat in Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary is moderate. The majority of the respondents were aware of biodiversity, the different ecosystems present in their location, and the importance and benefits of marine resources in their daily lives. However, there were still some gaps in knowledge, such as the role of coastal habitat in supporting ecosystems and the ecological functions of coastal biodiversity.

The respondents are aware of the importance of protecting and conserving natural resources, and are willing to take action to do so. It also indicates that there is a recognition of the interdependence between humans and the environment, as well as the need for responsible management of natural resources. The survey reveals that some concerning attitudes, such as the tendency to entrust the protection of the environment to others who are deemed more knowledgeable, or the tendency to blame others for environmental calamities caused by irresponsible actions. These attitudes suggest a need for further education and awareness-raising on personal

responsibility and the importance of individual actions in protecting the environment.

Figure 5. Attitude tendency to entrust the protection of the environment.

The respondents also identified various ecosystems present in their location, including mangroves, seagrasses, coral reefs, mudflats areas, among others. This suggests that the respondents have some level of knowledge about the different types of ecosystems and habitats in their area. The survey showed that most respondents recognized the importance and benefits of marine resources in their location. Specifically, they identified that marine resources are sources of food, livelihood and that they provide protection against storms, serve as a recreational area, and contribute to the economy. This indicates that respondents are aware of the significant role that marine resources play in their daily lives.

Figure 6. Importance and benefits of marine resources.

The respondents recognized the importance of specific ecosystems such as mangroves, seagrasses, and coral reefs. These ecosystems provide natural breakwaters, shelter and habitat for various animals, and support the growth and survival of different marine species. This indicates a level of awareness of the ecological functions of these ecosystems. The data also suggests that there is still room for improvement in terms of understanding the different aspects of biodiversity and their role in supporting life and the environment.

For example, only 29 out of 30 respondents identified the characteristic of seagrasses. Additionally, only 19 out of 30 respondents believed that the condition of mangroves affects the source of food for various animals, which may indicate a lack of understanding of the ecological role of mangroves in supporting food webs.

Figure 7. Condition of Mangroves.

On mangrove use, all respondents reported that they do not cut down mangroves to use as firewood, indicating a positive attitude towards mangrove conservation. Mangroves are important ecosystems that provide numerous benefits, including protecting shorelines from erosion and serving as habitats for a variety of wildlife. This finding suggests that the community recognizes the value of mangroves and is taking steps to conserve them.

Figure 8. Mangrove Use.

On tree planting activities 18 out of 30 respondents participate in tree planting activities in their community, which is a positive attitude towards reforestation and

environmental conservation. Tree planting is an important activity that helps to restore degraded ecosystems, mitigate climate change, and provide numerous benefits for local communities. This finding suggests that the community recognizes the importance of reforestation and is taking action to promote it.

A study on the evaluation and perceived effects of coastal resource management (CRM) projects on the southern part of Masbate Island, Philippines, was carried out by Balilo Jr., et al. in 2023. In terms of the community's knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) concerning coastal resource management, the goal of the project was to evaluate the success of coastal resource management (CRM) initiatives in the southern portion of Masbate Island, Philippines. The study's findings revealed that most participants had a modest degree of CRM expertise, with a mean score of 2.66 out of 4. The study also discovered that the respondents' perceptions of CRM were largely favorable, with a mean rating of 3.58 out of 5.

In terms of practices, the respondents reported engaging in sustainable fishing practices and coastal resource management activities such as the establishment of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and mangrove reforestation. The study also found that the respondents' level of education and participation in CRM programs had a significant positive effect on their knowledge, attitudes, and practices towards coastal resource management.

Both studies aim to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of community members towards protecting and conserving coastal resources. The KAP of SAMAPUSI Inc for Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary focus on the fisherfolk organization members, while the study Balilo., et al (2023) assessed the effectiveness of Coastal Resource Management (CRM) programs in the southern part of Masbate

Island. Both studies found that community members had a moderate level of knowledge about coastal resource management, indicating a need for further education and awareness-raising initiatives.

Also found that community members had positive attitudes towards protecting and conserving coastal resources, recognizing the importance and benefits of these resources. However, the study of Balilo., et al (2023) found that increasing knowledge can lead to more positive attitudes. In terms of practices, both studies found that community members engaged in activities to protect and conserve coastal resources. Both studies suggest that there is a need for continued education and awareness-raising initiatives to increase knowledge and understanding of coastal resource management, as well as a need for promoting sustainable practices and wider participation in conservation efforts.

The third objectives is to provide policy recommendations based on the findings of the study that can enhance the implementation and effectiveness management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. The result shown the importance of government programs in promoting environmental protection and conservation, with a significant number of respondents participating in such programs on a monthly basis. The reasons for participating in these programs vary, with some respondents considering it their obligation, while others participate to learn new information or gain clarity.

Figure 9. Participating on government programs.

The data revealed that 21 out of 30 respondents are aware of biodiversity, indicating a moderate level of understanding about the concept. However, there were still 7 respondents who are not aware and 2 who have no idea about biodiversity. When asked about what comprises biodiversity, the majority of the respondents (21 out of 30) identified animals and small organisms as part of it. This is not surprising since animals are often the most visible and recognizable part of biodiversity. However, it is worth noting that only 7 respondents identified plants and trees as part of biodiversity, indicating a potential lack of awareness of the role of plants and trees in supporting ecosystems and providing various benefits such as oxygen production and carbon sequestration.

Active community involvement participated by all the members of SAMAPUSI Inc. in all the activities with regards to the protection and conservation of biodiversity. This shown that indicates a high level of awareness and engagement towards environmental conservation. A positive finding that the community values biodiversity and recognizes the importance of protecting it. Community involvement is essential for promoting sustainable development and conservation, and this finding suggests that the community is taking an active role in these efforts.

The survey question also asked respondents about their willingness to seek help from authorities if they witness illegal activities that harm the environment in their area. Out of 30 respondents, 25 answered that they would always seek help from authorities, while 5 respondents said that they would sometimes seek help. No respondents said that they would not seek help.

Figure 10. Respondent willingness to seek help.

This result indicates a generally positive attitude towards reporting illegal environmental activities to authorities. The majority of respondents recognize the importance of protecting the environment and are willing to take action to address harmful practices. However, it is worth noting that there are still a small number of respondents who only sometimes seek help, indicating that there may be some barriers to reporting illegal activities that need to be addressed.

The study on the Perception of Fishers towards Marine Reserve in Iloilo Coastal Communities, Central Philippines aimed to assess the perceptions of fishers towards marine. The fishers had mixed perceptions towards marine reserves, with some perceiving them as beneficial for their livelihoods and the environment, while others perceived them as restrictive and negatively impacting their livelihoods. Factors that

influenced fishers' perceptions included their level of participation in the management of marine reserves, their awareness of the benefits of marine reserves, and their trust in the local government and non-governmental organizations involved in marine conservation efforts. The authors recommend that efforts to establish marine reserves should take into account the perceptions and concerns of local fishers, and that communication and engagement with local communities should be a key component of marine conservation initiatives.

The study on the Perception of Fishers towards Marine Reserve in Iloilo Coastal Communities, Central Philippines and the Buntod Reef management study have different research objectives and focus on different aspects of marine conservation. The Perception of Fishers towards Marine Reserve in Iloilo Coastal Communities study assesses the perceptions of fishers towards marine reserves, while the Buntod Reef management study aims to provide policy recommendations for the management of a specific marine sanctuary. Both studies highlights the importance of community involvement in marine conservation efforts. The Perception of Fishers towards Marine Reserve in Iloilo Coastal Communities study found that fishers who were more involved in the management of marine reserves tended to have more positive perceptions of them, while the Buntod Reef management study found that active community involvement was essential for promoting sustainable development and conservation. Additionally, both studies highlights the importance of awareness and education campaigns in promoting marine conservation.

The Perception of Fishers towards Marine Reserve in Iloilo Coastal Communities study found that fishers who were more aware of the benefits of marine reserves tended to have more positive perceptions, while the Buntod Reef management study found that government programs promoting environmental

protection and conservation were important in increasing awareness and engagement towards environmental conservation.

X. RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the study highlights the importance of understanding the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of fisherfolk organization members in the management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. The study shows that while fisherfolk organization members have a moderate level of knowledge, positive attitudes, and good practices towards marine resource management, there are still gaps and areas for improvement.

The policy recommendations provided can help enhance the implementation and effectiveness of the management of the sanctuary. Strengthening education and awareness-raising efforts, developing effective regulations and policies, providing alternative livelihood options, strengthening waste management practices, and strengthening partnerships and collaboration can all contribute to sustainable management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems.

The importance of assessing the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of fisherfolk organization members in protecting marine habitats such as Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. The results of the study suggest that while there is a moderate level of knowledge and positive attitudes towards protecting the marine environment, there are still some gaps in understanding the various aspects of biodiversity and the ecological functions of specific ecosystems. It is essential to provide education and awareness-raising efforts to address these gaps in knowledge and enhance the understanding of fisherfolk organization members regarding their role in protecting the marine habitat. In addition, promoting collaborative shared management among fisherfolk organizations and other stakeholders can lead to more effective protection and management of marine habitats.

The study on the knowledge, attitude, and practices of fisherfolk organization members in terms of collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems showed that there is a need a room for improvement in terms of their knowledge and understanding of the biodiversity and ecological functions of different marine ecosystems and to sustain the effective management collaboration effort, practices between the City Government of Masbate and the Samahan ng Mangingisda ng Puro Sinalikway (SAMAPUSI Inc.). However, the respondents generally have positive attitudes towards the management of marine resources and are willing to participate in conservation efforts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following policy recommendations are suggested to enhance the implementation and effectiveness management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary. For the first objective in determining the knowledge, attitude and practices of fisherfolk organization members in terms of collaborative shared management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary ecosystems. Recommendation are the following:

1. Increase education awareness. To address the gaps in knowledge and understanding of biodiversity, marine resources and ecosystems, and the importance of protecting natural resources, there is a need for more education and awareness-raising initiatives. This can be done through various means, such as community-based information campaigns and the use of social media platforms.

2. Community participation. Encouraging community participation in conservation efforts can help in achieving environmental sustainability. The City of Masbate and non-government organizations can collaborate with the Samagan ng Mangingisda ng Puro Sinalikway to develop and implement conservation programs that address local environmental concerns.

3. Regular monitoring and evaluation. The City Government of Masbate shall be conducting a regular monitoring and evaluation of environmental programs that can help assess the effectiveness of conservation efforts and identify areas for improvement. This will also help in ensuring sustainability.

The level of knowledge, attitudes, and practices and their roles in protecting the marine habitat in Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary, encourage the fisherfolk organization members to take personal responsibility for protecting the environment and not entrust the protection of the environment to others who are deemed more knowledgeable and strengthen cooperation and collaboration between fisherfolk organizations, local government units, and other stakeholders should be strengthened and enhance to promote better management and protection of marine resources in the area. This can be achieved through regular meetings and consultations to develop strategies and action plans for marine conservation.

The importance of government programs in promoting environmental protection and conservation, with many respondents participating in such programs. Therefore, it is recommended that the government and other stakeholders increase funding and support for conservation efforts in the sanctuary, including regular clean-up drives and the establishment of sustainable livelihood programs for the fisherfolk community.

Foster collaboration among stakeholders. The study also reveals that some respondents tend to entrust the protection of the environment to others who are deemed more knowledgeable, indicating a need for greater collaboration among stakeholders. It is recommended that the government and sanctuary management work closely with the fisherfolk organization members, local government units, and other stakeholders to foster collaboration and ensure effective management of the sanctuary.

By implementing these policy recommendations, it is hoped that the management of Buntod Reef Marine Sanctuary will be enhanced, and the conservation and protection of the sanctuary's marine resources will be improved for the benefit of the fisherfolk community and the environment.

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